

On Colloidal Electrolytes: An Attempt to Account for their Electroviscous Effect under Different Conditions

B. N. GHOSH

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta-9

Manuscript received 26 March 1976; revised 7 July 1976; accepted 2 August 1976

Combining the equation proposed by the author for the variation of specific conductivity of a colloidal electrolyte with its concentration, C , with the Smoluchowski equation for electroviscous effect, equations have been deduced which account quantitatively for the variation of η_{sp}/C (specific viscosity/ C) with the concentration, C , of a colloidal electrolyte in the absence as well as in the presence of an added strong electrolyte.

The equations have been found fairly satisfactory when tested by using the data available in the literature on the variation of η_{sp}/C or η_{sp}/ϕ with C or ϕ for sols of sodium thymus nucleate sodium gum arabate, arabic acid, polyacrylic acids of different degrees of polymerisation, silver iodide and monodisperse polystyrene lattices prepared by emulsion polymerisation using Na-steprate, as emulsifier.

A considerable amount of theoretical and experimental work has been done on the electroviscous property of colloidal electrolytes.¹⁻¹⁷ It has been observed (1) that in a pure (i.e., well-dialysed) sol of a colloidal electrolyte the electro-viscous effect increases as the concentration C of the sol is diminished, (2) that addition of even a small amount of a strong electrolyte to it (i.e., the sol) markedly lowers the electroviscous effect, and (3) that in the presence of a given concentration of an added electrolyte the electroviscous effect increases as the concentration of the colloid is increased.

According to Stone-Masui and Watilon¹⁶ the existing theories of electroviscous effect cannot be applied to a pure sol as the thickness of the electrical double layer needed for their application cannot be calculated.

Derivation of the equations

In this paper an attempt will be made to account quantitatively for the variation of electroviscous effect of a colloidal electrolyte with its concentration first in the absence of an added electrolyte and then in its presence.

Von Smoluchowski's extension of Einstein equation may be written as follows:

$$\eta_{sp} = K\phi \left[1 + \frac{1}{a^2 \eta_0 \lambda} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_{sp} denotes the specific viscosity of the sol, K a constant equal to 2.5 for spherical particles, ϕ the volume fraction, ζ the electrokinetic potential

of the colloidal particles, a , their radius D , η_0 and λ , the dielectric constant, viscosity and specific conductivity respectively of the dispersion medium.

It may be mentioned that Briggs^{11,12} in his investigation on electroviscous effect has taken λ as the specific conductivity of the sol of the colloidal electrolyte. We shall also take λ as the specific conductivity of the sol of the colloidal electrolyte for the reason that a considerable portion of the conduction current which tends to annual the distortion of the double layer caused by the laminar flow must pass through the ion atmosphere close to the surface of the colloidal particles where owing to high concentration of the counter ions the specific conductivity is much higher than that of the intermicellar solution. Thus the conduction current flows partly through the ion atmosphere and partly through the intermicellar solution and hence λ should be taken as the specific conductivity of the sol, it being made up of two parts one part contributed by the colloidal particles and the other part by the intermicellar solution.

It has been shown by the author in previous publications¹⁹⁻²² that the variation of specific conductivity λ of a colloidal electrolyte with dilution can be represented by the following equation:

$$\lambda = \theta \lambda_s + (1 - \theta) \lambda_t \quad \dots (2)$$

where λ_s is a constant* and represents the specific conductivity of the ion atmosphere close to the surface of the particle, λ_t , the specific conductivity

* λ_s is constant for a pure sol.

of the intermicellar solution and θ , the fraction per unit area of the surface of the electrode of the conductivity cell covered by the double layers of the colloidal particles. θ is equal to $C/(K_0+C)$ where K_0 is a constant and C the concentration (unit arbitrary) of the colloidal particles

Substituting this value of λ in equation (1) and putting $A = (1/a^2\eta_0)(\zeta D/2\pi)^2$ and $\phi = Cv/V$ where v is the volume per unit concentration of the colloidal electrolyte and V the total volume of the solution it (eqn. 1) may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{v}{V} \left[1 + \frac{A}{\theta\lambda_s + (1-\theta)\lambda_t} \right] \quad \dots (3)$$

It may be pointed out that in a pure sol of a colloidal electrolyte $\lambda_s \gg \lambda_t$ and that when C only i.e., θ is increased A , λ_s and λ_t do not change. Therefore, it follows from equation (3) that at constant V when C i.e. θ is increased η_{sp}/C should diminish in agreement with observation.

Substituting $\theta = C/(K_0+C)$ in equation (3) the following equation is obtained

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{v}{V} \left[1 + \frac{A(K_0+C)}{C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_t} \right] \quad \dots (4)$$

It may be pointed out that as θ represents a ratio and C in it can be expressed in an arbitrary unit therefore, at constant v/V one can write

$$\theta = C/(K_0+C) = C \frac{v}{V} / (K_0+C) \frac{v}{V} = \phi / (h + \phi)$$

where $h = K_0 \frac{v}{V}$.

Since v/V is a ratio therefore, the constant, h has the same dimension as K_0 . For spherical particles substituting this value of θ in equation (3) it may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/\phi = 2.5 \left[1 + \frac{A(h+\phi)}{h\lambda_t + \phi\lambda_s} \right] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$= 2.5 \left[1 + \frac{A_1 + \beta\phi}{1 + \beta_0\phi} \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

In equation (6) $A_1 = A/\lambda_t$, $\beta = A/h\lambda_t$ and $\beta_0 = \frac{\lambda_s}{h\lambda_t}$

and they remain constant when the sol is diluted with the dispersion medium. When some strong/electrolyte, even in a small amount, is added to the system, A and λ_s may change only slightly, but λ_t increases sharply and so $A(h+\phi)/(h\lambda_t + \phi\lambda_s)$ in equation (5) and A_1 , β and β_0 in equation (6) diminish markedly and hence η_{sp}/ϕ also diminishes. As the concentration of the added electrolyte is increased* gradually, λ_t increases more and more and $\lambda_s\phi$ becomes less and less important and when the concentration of the added electrolyte is sufficiently high, $\lambda_s\phi$ becomes negligible compared to $h\lambda_t$. Under this

*As the concentration of the added electrolyte is increased, A and λ_s should decrease to some extent but not much.

condition equation (6) assumes the following linear form :

$$\eta_{sp}/\phi = 2.5[1 + A_1 + \beta\phi] \quad \dots (6a)$$

It may be mentioned that if the sol is diluted with an electrolyte solution of given concentration then ϕ changes but A_1 , β and β_0 do not change.

When the shape of the colloidal particles and the volume fraction are not known, equation (4) may be adapted to experimental conditions, under which C alone is varied, in the following way. After some simplification equation (4) may be expressed as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{v}{V} \left[\frac{K_0(A + \lambda_t) + (A + \lambda_s)c}{K_0\lambda_t + c\lambda_s} \right] \quad \dots (7)$$

$$= K \frac{v}{V} \left[\left(\frac{A + \lambda_s}{\lambda_s} \right) \frac{K_0(A + \lambda_t)/(A + \lambda_s) + c}{(K_0\lambda_t/\lambda_s) + c} \right]$$

$$= K_1 \left[\frac{m + C}{m_0 + C} \right] \quad \dots (8)$$

or,

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K_1 \frac{1 + m/C}{1 + m_0/C} \quad \dots (8a)$$

where $K_1 = K \frac{v}{V} \left(\frac{A + \lambda_s}{\lambda_s} \right)$, $m = K_0(A + \lambda_t)/(A + \lambda_s)$

and $m_0 = K_0\lambda_t/\lambda_s$. For a pure sol $m > m_0$ and K_1 , m and m_0 remain constant when the concentration C of the colloid is varied. Addition of an electrolyte changes each one of them, but at a fixed concentration of an added electrolyte each one of them remains constant. The same remark also applies to A_1 , β and β_0 of equation (6) or (6a).

It may also be noted, for reasons stated already, that in the presence of a sufficient quantity of an added electrolyte C in the denominator of equation (8) becomes negligible compared to m_0 and the equation then assumes the linear form :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K_1[A_2 + \beta_2 C] \quad \dots (8b)$$

where $A_2 = m/m_0$ and $\beta_2 = 1/m_0$. The application of the equations deduced is discussed in the following section.

Notes on the data recorded in the Tables

In Table 1 are recorded the data of Jong and Gwan⁷ on sodium thymus nucleate at 43°. In column 1 the equation used, the value of the constants in the equation etc. are mentioned. Column 2 contains the concentration C of the colloid as expressed by the authors⁷ in terms of the highest investigated concentration as the unit. η_s and η_0 denote respectively the viscosity of the sol and that of water.

In Table 2 are recorded the data of Kruyt and Winkler⁸ on gum arabic sol at 25°. In this case C represents the concentration in grams of the gum (after correction for moisture and ash constant) per 100 ml of the sol.

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY OF SODIUM THYMUS NUCLEATE SOL

Equation and its constants	C	η_s/η_0	Values of η_{sp}/C	
			Observed	Calcd.
Equation (8)	1.0000	1.582	0.583	0.598
$K_1 = 0.35$	0.7460	1.491	0.659	0.670
$m = 0.95$	0.4956	1.399	0.805	0.790
$m_0 = 0.14$	0.2462	1.268	1.091	1.085
	0.1264	1.182	1.440	1.414
	0.0628	1.110	1.752	1.748
	0.0314	1.065	2.070	2.006
	0.0154	1.034	2.208	2.174

TABLE 2.—VISCOSITY OF GUM ARABIC ACID SOL.

Equation and its constants	C	η_s/η_0	Values of η_{sp}/C	
			Observed	Calcd.
Equation (8)	1.720	2.015	0.59	0.60
$K_1 = 0.577$	0.860	1.563	0.65	0.64
$m = 0.13$	0.430	1.321	0.75	0.70
$m_0 = 0.035$	0.215	1.185	0.86	0.80
	0.107	1.104	0.97	0.97
	0.053	1.060	1.13	1.21

In Tables 3, 4 and 5 are recorded the data of Kern⁹ on polyacrylic acids of different degrees of polymerisation (D.P.) 200, 800 and 1000 at 20°. The concentration C of the polyacrylic acids has been expressed by the author⁹ in grund-molarity i.e., 72 grams per liter.

TABLE 3—VISCOSITY OF SOL OF POLYACRYLIC ACID D.P. 200

Equation and its constants	C	Values of η / C	
		Observed	Calcd.
Equation (8)	0.1	5.1	5.4
$K_1 = 4.2$	0.05	6.8	6.5
	0.01	18.0	15.7
$m = 0.028$	0.008	20.5	18.5
	0.006	25.5	23.1
$m_0 = 0.0002$	0.004	34.0	32.0
	0.002	57.0	57.0
	0.001	92.0	101.0

TABLE 4—VISCOSITY OF SOL OF POLYACRYLIC ACID D.P. 800

Equation used etc.	C	Values of η / C	
		Observed	Calcd.
Equation (8)	0.1	27.4	29.4
$K_1 = 19.0$	0.075	32.1	32.8
$m = 0.056$	0.05	40.2	39.5
	0.04	46.2	44.6
$m_0 = 0.00093$	0.03	57.4	52.8
	0.02	75.0	69.0
	0.01	122.0	115.0
	0.006	163.0	170.0
	0.003	263.0	285.0

TABLE 5—VISCOSITY OF SOL OF POLYACRYLIC ACID D.P. 1000

Equation used etc.	C	Values of η_{sp}/C	
		Observed	Calcd.
Equation (8)	0.093	32.7	34.7
$K_1 = 19.8$	0.06	42.2	42.7
	0.04	56.3	53.8
$m = 0.072$	0.03	68.7	64.6
$m_0 = 0.00125$	0.02	88.5	85.7
	0.01	148.0	144.3
	0.006	218.0	213.0
	0.003	320.0	349.0
	0.001	640.0	642.0

The data taken from Table 2 of Briggs¹¹ paper on sodium arabate are recorded in Table 6. The concentration C of the colloid has been expressed in grams per ml. of the sol and measurements have been made at 25°.

TABLE 6—VISCOSITY OF SODIUM GUM ARABATE SOL.

Equation used etc.	C	η_{sp} observed	Values of η_{sp}/C	
			Observed	Calcd.
Equation (8)	0.0025	0.511	204	203
$K_1 = 122$	0.00375	0.700	187	180
	0.0050	0.892	178	167
$m = 0.0028$	0.0075	1.118	149	153
$m_0 = 0.0007$	0.0100	1.480	148	146

In Table 7 are recorded the data on sodium thymus nucleate sols containing 5 milli-equivalents per litre of KCl. The concentration C of the colloid has been expressed by the authors⁷ in terms of the highest concentration used as unit.

TABLE 7—VISCOSITY OF SODIUM THYMUS NUCLEATE SOL WITH 5 MILLIEQUIVALENT/L KCl

Equation etc.	C	η_s/η_0	Values of η_{sp}/C		
			Observed	Calculated	
				eqn.(8)	eqn.(8b)
Equation (8)	1.0000	1.292	0.292	0.290	0.299
$K_1 = 0.37$	0.7097	1.203	0.287	0.280	0.282
$m = 1, m_0 = 1.55$	0.4967	1.140	0.282	0.272	0.270
Equation (8b)	0.3271	1.089	0.272	0.262	0.260
$K_1 m/m_0 = 0.241$	0.2443	1.063	0.258	0.257	0.255
$K_1/m_0 = 0.058$	0.1620	1.040	0.247	0.251	0.250

Tables 8 and 9 contain Briggs data on sodium gum arabate sols at 25°. Each of the sols in Table 8 contains 2 milligram equivalents of NaCl and each of these in Table 9 contains 5 milliequivalents of NaCl per litre. The concentration C of the colloid has been expressed in grams per ml.

TABLE 8—VISCOSITY SODIUM GUM ARABATE SOL. WITH 2 MILLIEQUIVALENT/L OF NaCl

Equation etc.	C	η/η_0	Values of η/C	
			Observed	Calcd.
Equation (8)	0.0025	1.155	62.0	62.9
$K_1 = 120$	0.00375	1.255	68.0	68.9
$m = 0.003$	0.005	1.375	75.0	73.8
$m_0 = 0.008$	0.0075	1.612	81.6	81.2
	0.010	1.861	86.1	86.7

TABLE 9—VISCOSITY OF SODIUM GUM ARABATE SOL WITH 5 MILLIEQUIVALENT/L NaCl

Equation etc.	C	η/η_0	Values of η/C .		
			Observed	Calculated	
				eqn.(8)	eqn.(8b)
Equation (8)					
$K_1 = 105$	0.0025	1.108	43.2	42.5	42.8
$m = 0.0054$	0.00375	1.171	45.6	46.3	45.6
$m_0 = 0.017$	0.0075	1.408	54.5	55.3	54.3
Equation (8b)					
$K_1 m/m_0 = 37,$ $K_1/m_0 = 2300$	0.010	1.602	60.2	59.9	60.0

Table 10 contains data of Harmsen, Schooten and Overbeek¹³ on AgI sol at 25° taken from Table II-1 of their paper. Each of the sols contains 0.035 milligram ions of H⁺ per liter. In Table 10 the volume fraction is denoted by ϕ and $(A_1 + \beta\phi)/(1 + \beta_0\phi)$ by f .

TABLE 10—VISCOSITY OF AgI SOL WITH 0.035 MILLIGRAM IONS OF H⁺ PER LITER

Equation etc.	ϕ	Values of η_{sp}/ϕ		f
		Observed	Calcd.	
Equation (6)	Lt $y = 0$	—	2.56	0.024
$A_1 = 0.024$	0.00107	2.60	2.80	0.12
$\beta = 91.4$	0.00209	3.90	3.00	0.21
$\beta_0 = 11.1$	0.00411	3.63	3.46	0.39
	0.00797	4.39	4.23	0.69
	0.0158	5.15	5.63	1.26
	0.0299	7.74	7.68	2.07

It may be pointed out that all the sols, the data of which are recorded in the Tables 7–10, contain added electrolyte and their η_{sp}/C or η_{sp}/ϕ increases as the colloid content of the sols rises.

Determination of the constants in the equations

For the pure sols, the data of which are recorded in the Tables 1–6, equation (8) has been used. In these cases, it follows from theoretical consideration that $m \gg m_0$ and so for high values of C , m_0 can be neglected compared to C and the equation $\eta_{sp}/C = K_1(m+C)/C$ may be used. Using this equation, for two known values of C and the corresponding experimentally determined values of η_{sp}/C , the constants, K_1 and m can be found. Next m_0 can be

found by solving equation (8) using a very low value of C and the corresponding experimentally determined value of η_{sp}/C . After these approximate values of K_1 , m and m_0 are found they are improved by following the method of successive approximation.

For the sols containing an added electrolyte $m_0 > m$ and this fact is utilised for finding the constants in the equations (6) or (8) by trial. When the concentration of the added electrolyte is sufficiently high the equations assume linear form and the constants in them can be easily found.

Discussion

The concentrations of the colloidal electrolytes recorded in the Tables 1 to 10 are below the level at which second order electroviscous effect owing to the interaction of the double layers of the particles begins to appear. In all the systems recorded above, we are, therefore, dealing with the first order electroviscous effect. It will be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables that the agreement between the observed and the calculated values of η_{sp}/C or η_{sp}/ϕ is fairly satisfactory.

When the sols are pure (that is no electrolyte has been added to them) the values of η_{sp}/C decreases as the concentration C of the colloid increases and this variation of η_{sp}/C with C can be quantitatively accounted for by equation (8). A comparison of the data recorded in the Tables 6 and 8 shows that addition of even a small amount of an electrolyte causes a marked decrease in η_{sp}/C . At a constant concentration of an added electrolyte the variation of η_{sp}/C or η_{sp}/ϕ with C or ϕ recorded in the Tables 8 and 10 can be accounted for by the corresponding equation (8) or (6).

Attention may also be drawn to the variation of η_{sp}/C with C of the systems sodium thymus nucleate and sodium gum arabate recorded in the Tables 7 and 9. Each of these sols contains 5 milliequivalents per liter of a uni-univalent salt and the data can be accounted for approximately by both the equations (8) and (8b). It seems λ_s of sodium thymus nucleate is greater than that of sodium gum arabate.

Some of the data of Harmsen, Schooten and Overbeek¹³ on AgI sol are recorded in Table 10. The particles of the sol are spherical in shape and the sol contains HI, the H⁺ ion concentration being 0.035 milligram ion per litre. The increase of η_{sp}/ϕ with the increase of ϕ can be accounted for by equation (6). It will be noticed that f which represents the contribution of the electroviscous effect increases as ϕ increases. In this case the second order electroviscous effect appears when the value of ϕ is higher than 0.0299 which is the highest value recorded in Table 10.

Reference may also be made to some of the data of Stone-Masui and Watillon¹⁶ on monodisperse polystyrene lattices prepared by emulsion polymerisation using Na-stearate as emulsifier. Systems 4 and 7 (in Table 3 of their paper) have spherical particles of the same diameter but contain 0.05 and 0.2 millimoles per liter of NaClO₄. In each of these systems

the relation between η_{sp}/ϕ and ϕ is linear which is in agreement with equation (6a). For the system 4 which contains less NaClO_4 , $A_1 = 1.0$ and $\beta = 426$ and for the system 7 which contains more NaClO_4 , $A_1 = 0.18$ and $\beta = 79$.

References

1. A. EINSTEIN, *Ann. Physik.*, 1911, **34**, 592.
2. M. VON. SMOLUCHOWSKI, *Kolloid. Z.*, 1916, **18**, 194.
3. W. KRASNY-ERGEN, *Kolloid. Z.*, 1936, **74**, 172.
4. B. N. FINKELSTEIN and M. P. OHURSN, *Acta Physico-chim. U.R.R.S.*, 1942, **17**, 1.
5. F. BOOTH, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1950, **A203**, 533.
6. N. STREET, *J. Colloid. Sic.*, 1958, **13**, 828.
7. H. G. BUNGENBERG, DE JONG and ONG SIAN GWAN, *Kolloidchem. Beihefte*, 1930, **31**, 89.
8. H. R. KRUYT and K. C. WINKLER, *Kolloidchem. Beihefte*, 1931, **32**, 374.
9. W. KERN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1937-38, **A180-181**, 283.
10. H. B. BULL, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 80.
11. D. R. BRIGGS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, **45**, 866.
12. D. R. BRIGGS and M. HANIG, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1944, **48**, 1.
13. G. J. HARMSSEN, J. VAN SCHOOTEN and J. TH. OVERBEEK, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1953, **8**, 73.
14. A. J. RUTGERS and P. NAGELS, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1958, **13**, 149.
15. P. MUKHERJEE, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1964, **19**, 724.
16. J. STONE-MASUI and A. WATLON, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1969, **29**, 536.
17. M. SENGUPTA and S. A. ALI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 764.
18. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 359.
19. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 565.
20. B. N. GHOSH, *Proc. Indian Nat. Sci. Acad.*, 1972, **A30**, 45.
21. B. N. GHOSH, A. C. S. Symposium Series, Colloid Dispersions and Micellar Behaviour, 1975, **9**, 316.